

The Worldwide LHC Computing Grid input to the ESPP24-26

Submitted by:

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Abstract

The Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) is the global infrastructure, developed and operated over the last two decades, that provides the computing infrastructure for the processing and analysis of data from the LHC experiments. The WLCG Collaboration comprises the sites being part of the infrastructure and the LHC experiments, with a thin management layer. The notable achievement of WLCG has been to successfully meet the needs of the LHC experiments by the integration of globally distributed Exascale-level resources, with services and software within a trust framework that transcends site and national boundaries. The success of WLCG has relied on innovation, leadership, collaboration, agility, and the confidence of the community and funding agencies to commit to the endeavour as an essential step towards the success of the physics initiatives. Today, WLCG has evolved from the initial Grid of uniform systems to a much more diverse infrastructure, able to support the experiments via owned centers, public and private clouds, and HPC systems. WLCG is still a rather unique facility in science, but as the needs of other communities grow beyond what can be provided by individual facilities, they too have started to tackle similar issues. The future brings new challenges in terms of scale, technology, funding, sustainability, and the integration and coexistence with related communities. This note is the WLCG input to the ESPP 2024-2026 process and elaborates on the WLCG 2024-2027 Strategy Document approved by the WLCG Overview Board in June 2024. While the ESPP process looks at a much larger timespan, in the context of computing the most significant challenge of the next two decades is the HL-LHC, starting in 2030. The next few years will be vital for the commissioning of the software and the computing infrastructure for HL-LHC, which is why we focus on this shorter time span.

Introduction

The Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) is the global infrastructure developed and operated over the last two decades that provides the computing infrastructure for the processing and analysis of data from the LHC experiments. The WLCG Collaboration comprises the sites being part of the infrastructure and the LHC experiments, with a thin management layer. The notable achievement of WLCG has been to successfully meet the needs of the LHC experiments by the integration of globally distributed Exascale-level resources with services and software, within a trust framework that transcends site and national boundaries. WLCG is currently of the scale of over a million cores and more than two Exabytes of storage. It extends across 160 sites in over 40 countries and is underpinned by 65 Memoranda of Understanding signed by funding agencies across the world. The success of WLCG has relied on innovation, leadership, collaboration, agility, and the confidence of the community and funding agencies to commit to the endeavour as an essential step towards the success of the physics initiatives.

Today, WLCG has evolved from the initial Grid of uniform systems to a much more diverse infrastructure, able to support the experiments via owned centers, public and private clouds, and HPC systems. From the architecture point of view, it has been able to move from the off-the-shelf Linux systems at the start of LHC, to a diverse environment supporting multiple architectures, accelerators, and special use cases such as analysis and machine learning developments, while remaining in production at all times. WLCG is still a rather unique facility in science, but as the needs of other communities grow beyond what can be provided by individual facilities, they too have started to tackle similar issues. The future brings new challenges in terms of scale, technology, funding, sustainability, and the integration and coexistence with related communities. This note is the WLCG input to the ESPP 2024-2026 process and elaborates on the WLCG 2024-2027 Strategy Document approved by the WLCG Overview Board in June 2024. While the ESPP process looks at a much larger timespan, in the context of computing the most significant challenge of the next two decades is the HL-LHC, starting in 2030. The next few years will be vital for the commissioning of the software and the computing infrastructure for HL-LHC, which is why we focus on this shorter time span.

HEP Challenges

The demand for scientific computing capacity in HEP continues to increase. For the LHC physics program, the compute core-hours required by two of the four large experiments as a function of time are shown in Fig. 1, which shows increases of 10x-20x are expected. During LHC Run-2 (2015-2018) the funding agencies of the LHC experiments made it clear that funding beyond a constant budget should not be expected during Run-2 or beyond. Such “flat funding” was sufficient for the computing resources needed to extract the physics from Run-2 and, whilst we expect it also to be adequate for Run-3, it is unlikely to be sufficient for HL-LHC unless there are

major evolutions in the application software, the computing services, and the infrastructure. The most recent public resource projections from the ATLAS and CMS experiments for HL-LHC are shown in Fig 1. They are compared with the expected available resources in the flat budget scenario, considering a moderate increase in the computing performance per unit cost over the coming years. WLCG would not be able to cope with the future needs of the LHC experiments within the flat funding constraints, without the evolution mentioned above.

Figure 1: the ATLAS (top) and CMS (bottom) latest public projections for the computing (left) and disk storage (right) needed for the HL-LHC. The projections were produced in early 2022 based on a revisited LHC schedule with a later start of HL-LHC by 18 months from earlier predictions. They show projections in different R&D scenarios. Sources: <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2802918>, <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2815292>.

We also note that several HENP (High Energy and Nuclear Physics) projects, as well as others in the field of Astronomy and Astro-particle physics, are expected to start collecting significant quantities of data in the next decade. Those projects also embrace a distributed computing model and the needs of some are comparable to that of the LHC experiments. They share many of the same computing challenges faced by the LHC, as well as several of the facilities providing storage and compute and the network infrastructure that glues them into a distributed computing system.

In the medium-term future, WLCG must continue to:

- Support the core use cases of the ongoing LHC programme, whilst evolving the infrastructure to meet the needs of the HL-LHC.
- Identify, explore, and exploit techniques to increase the output of the infrastructure without significantly increasing the cost, by optimising the operational effort.
- Evolve services to benefit from advancing technologies, for example with a careful evaluation of in-house vs commercial tools.
- Increasingly embrace heterogeneous architectures and include diverse types of facilities.
- Develop methods to reduce our energy footprint and the CO₂ emissions.
- Collaborate with other communities representing sciences, software, and digital infrastructures, to share R&D and operational aspects where mutually beneficial.

WLCG Strategy

The WLCG Collaboration has prepared a strategy document for the period 2024-2027, approved in 2024 by its Collaboration Board and its Overview Board¹. To enact the strategy, a set of 33 actions has been identified, covering Service Operations, Technical Evolution, Finance, Infrastructure, Community Relationships, Software & Middleware, Governance, Environmental Sustainability, Risks, and Impact. Some of these are matters internal to WLCG; others are outward facing and intersect with issues addressed in the European Strategy Update. Of particular relevance are the connections between WLCG and other large-scale scientific communities; the co-location of resources and the use of common facilities; the role of HPC; the adoption of new technology; and the issue of environmental sustainability. We address these in the sections below, with the main directions summarized here:

- Maintain a focus on evolving and optimising current operations to deliver high availability resources to the LHC experiments. Our strategy implies continuity and continuous improvement.
- Ensure continuity and evolution through a programme of data challenges and improved monitoring. Our strategy is to avoid the accumulation of technical debt but without introducing disruptive changes.
- Reduce the cost, energy consumption, and carbon footprint of computing by being able to use a wide range of resources including Grid, public or private clouds, HPCs, and by expanding the architectures from the original x86 to include, for example, ARM, RISC-V, GPUs, and other technologies that may become available. Our strategy is to build agility so that opportunities can be seized.
- Modernise tools and services, benefiting from standards that are less HEP-specific where applicable. Our strategy is to profit where we can from well supported software that is used by the wider community, while carefully monitoring reliance on external dependencies.
- Increase collaboration with other communities, including formalising the status of associate partners in WLCG and increasing synergies with national and international initiatives developing large scale computing infrastructures. Our strategy is to benefit where we can from other relevant work.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/12623280>

- Review the structure and governance of WLCG; set up bodies, boards, and task forces to address problems and issues. Our strategy is to focus and optimise our existing strengths.

WLCG service operations

The WLCG service has reliably delivered the infrastructure needed to support the computing needs of the LHC experiments since 2006, providing services and resources with an availability and reliability that, as a whole, has exceeded the targets set in the memoranda of understanding signed with 65 funding agencies or institutes across the world. Since the start of the LHC, the volume of resources (CPU, storage, network) has increased by more than one order of magnitude, with no degradation in efficiency or performance. Operation of the hardware, software, services, and workflows is a shared activity between WLCG sites and the experiments; it is a key priority to optimise the effort needed to provide this infrastructure.

WLCG technical evolution

The operational success of WLCG is based, in part, on a conservative approach towards technical evolution. Since the facilities in WLCG are loosely coupled and the middleware development effort is distributed, new features are introduced to the infrastructure rather gradually to ensure continuity of operations. In terms of more disruptive innovation, there is sometimes resistance to changing a system that works. However, in the modern and rapidly evolving environment of distributed computing, WLCG risks accumulating additional technical debt if agility is not maintained. There are examples of initiatives put in place in preparation for HL-LHC, particularly in the area of Data Organization, Management and Access (DOMA), that have led to a successful R&D program with short- and long-term benefits. Broadening the scope of the modernisation of tools and services will be an essential ingredient for the future technical sustainability of the WLCG infrastructure. The capability to use different computing architectures will also play a key role. To coordinate this work, WLCG has recently created a Technical Board to enable stronger technical coordination through the development of a roadmap for the technical evolution, based on inputs from an open Technical Forum and the operational needs. WLCG has also set up a program of data challenges in preparation for HL-LHC that are a series of commissioning exercises of increasing complexity and scale, aimed at commissioning solutions for HL-LHC while not disrupting production activities. So far the challenges have focused on data transfers, but WLCG intends to start commissioning data access and analysis solutions soon.

Financial sustainability of WLCG services and infrastructure

The WLCG continues to receive strong support from its funding agencies, with resources being provided with a roughly constant annual budget. Additional resources are used by the experiments beyond the pledged capacity, particularly CPUs, either from additional resources at the Grid sites, or through the use of the experiment trigger-farms when available, or via the utilisation of external

clouds and HPC centres via opportunistic or managed patterns. However, globally, HEP budgets are not expected to expand significantly and LHC computing is likely to continue to be operated in the flat-funding mode of the last decade. In addition, the hardware markets in the last five years have not been very favourable, which has limited the increase in the volume of resources that could be purchased year-on-year. It has become increasingly important to monitor the evolution of market trends and hardware costs to prioritise the development areas in which the WLCG community should invest effort. Equally, it remains important for WLCG to develop the ability to make use of different types of architectures and facilities, where cost effective to do so, in order to be able to exploit as wide a range of opportunities as possible. Financial flexibility to purchase resources when needed, reflecting the expected data-taking schedule, would also help to optimise budgets.

Heterogeneous Grid infrastructure

The WLCG started its operations, circa 2004, as a Grid of uniform centers, mostly owned and operated by the HEP community, with similar policies, operational models, software solutions and interfaces. Over the last 20 years, the computing landscape has evolved significantly with the advent of solutions like public and commercial clouds, new CPU architectures with high efficiency and/or better performance, and more scientific initiatives deploying large-scale computing resources. In response, the WLCG has evolved towards a Grid of heterogeneous systems, which share well-defined high level interfaces, but can be very different at the implementation and operational levels. This trend is expected to continue, challenging the WLCG to incorporate increasingly diverse resources and services. The ability to address this challenge is crucial for the sustainability of LHC computing, as traditional Grid sites increasingly deliver only a fraction of the experiments' needs, and the experiments start to exploit the capabilities, and capacity, of these new facilities more fully.

The current organisation of WLCG facilities as Tier-0, Tier-1s and Tier-2s offers a simple but effective way to define the expected quality-of-service and target metrics, which are specified in the WLCG MoU. The Tier-0 and Tier-1s constitute the core data archive and delivery infrastructure. Whilst the network topology is today more flexible than originally anticipated, the connectivity across Tier-0 and Tier-1s is provided through dedicated links (the Optical Private Network - OPN). This guarantees enough capacity to enable the time-critical use cases. The vast majority of the remaining links between Tier-1s and Tier-2s are provided by the LHCONe overlay network, ensuring separation of WLCG traffic from other sciences in the Research and Education networks. The network infrastructure is one of the main assets in WLCG, enabling its core functions, but relies on good communication with network providers to ensure that the current and future needs of WLCG are well understood. In many places, HEP needs have driven the evolution of Research & Education networks, for the benefit of other sciences. Advances in network bandwidth and capabilities have enabled WLCG to evolve towards a much more flexible topology

than originally anticipated, a process that should continue, allowing more sites to support additional workflows, depending on their capabilities.

The processing and simulation of HEP data is largely performed on resource centers that the Funding Agencies own and operate. They are typically located at research laboratories or Universities, and the personnel operating them are directly affiliated to research or academic institutions. With the increase in the LHC performance since 2010, the extrapolated resource needs, when using the computing model defined by the experiments before the start of Run1, have increased in a non-sustainable way for the funding agencies. This has resulted in the concept of a budget cap for computing, the “flat budget”, and in large efforts from the experiments to optimize their processing needs without impacting the physics program. These efforts have been successful so far, and it is hoped that this can be extended to the HL-LHC era, pending the success of an articulated R&D program and a favourable technology and costing trend.

Even if the extrapolation holds, the HL-LHC physics program would benefit from a greater resource availability that can either complement or substitute contributions of the current centers. A clear candidate has been identified with HPC centers, deployed in many of the regions of WLCG interest, and generally operating resources that exceed those at WLCG centers. The capability to execute WLCG workflows on HPC centers depends on several factors: political (the handshaking with the centers; the definition of long term commitment of resources; and a recognized status for HEP as a strategic partner) and technical (the capability from the experiments to use accelerators like GPUs and FPGAs; and a validation of HPC centers as data intensive facilities). The WLCG is already moving in this direction and would benefit from further support for collaboration from CERN and HEP agencies, with the large HPC funding agencies and centers at the continental level in EU, USA and Asia.

The HEP community has a decade of experience integrating academic and commercial clouds; for the latter, there are several examples of sizable production activities where the resources were made available through grants, and a large-scale procurement was also made in the US. Such procurement allowed the integration between WLCG and cloud services to be improved; it also allowed the total cost of ownership to be studied, comparing on-premise services at WLCG centers versus cloud-procured resources. Although the cost of cloud resources is not currently favourable for bulk production compared to on-premise resources, the evolution of these costs should be monitored. This provides, however, the capability to absorb peaks of demand and procure non standard resources at a desired scale. The WLCG strategy is to continue to maintain the capability to integrate cloud resources; regularly monitor the evolution of cost; and leverage cloud solutions when needed. WLCG plans to discuss the risks related to reliance on commercial resources and agree the needed policies.

The discussion about specialised facilities and services for end-user analysis has been taking place for several years. Some large projects have developed an ecosystem for interactive analysis, and the functionalities of this ecosystem are being demonstrated through a set of challenges. The role of specialised facilities for Machine Learning have been only superficially discussed in WLCG and the resources for these activities have been provided opportunistically by some of the sites. In future, however, we expect the needs for ML/AI will increase both in terms of volume of resources but also variety of services. WLCG should therefore explore how such a facility could be hosted synergically at WLCG sites.

Heterogeneous facilities and particularly HPC centers increasingly provide significant capacity in the form of hardware accelerators (GPUs). This trend is expected to continue given the large needs of many communities for AI/ML resources. WLCG needs to establish the means and mechanisms to benchmark and pledge GPU resources and ensure that the provision of such heterogeneous resources matches the experiment's needs. In addition, non-x86 CPU resources such as ARM that is now deployed, and potentially RISC-V in the future, have good performance when looking at energy efficiency. WLCG sites will eventually need to also provide these heterogeneous architectures for supporting their sciences. It is vital for WLCG to be able to leverage heterogeneous compute architectures. The integration and portability work in the LHC offline software for heterogeneous architectures will be a lengthy process and also requires the engagement of all the major software projects (e.g. Geant4, ROOT, Event generators) and experiment software. It will require modernisation and refactoring of millions of lines of software and it will be an opportunity to streamline the code and possibly improve its performance. WLCG will continue engaging with the funding agencies to ensure that enough effort is provided to software development and modernisation. WLCG will also contribute in providing access to resources for heterogeneous software development, build systems, and validation platforms. Access mechanisms to validation and production resources should be integrated with the workflow management systems of the experiments.

To simplify interoperability between traditional WLCG sites and other more heterogeneous facilities, WLCG needs to modernise its own middleware to benefit from the most recent standards and community software solutions. This will also help reduce R&D and support costs. The high level plan is to move away from HEP specific solutions and consider the adoption of wider community standards, for example, for storage interfaces; the authentication and authorisation layer; and in future, possibly also the compute gateways. This process will further evolve WLCG towards being a Grid of heterogeneous centers. The WLCG plans at the same time to continue supporting products developed within our community that provide a competitive advantage with respect to generic industry standards. This is the case for example for storage solutions and data access protocols. WLCG also intends to support national initiatives for the evolution of the facilities. For example, many WLCG regions are going through a process of consolidation of resources, with storage provided by only a few centers and data being accessed by remote CPUs.

As part of the technical evolution of WLCG services, our community is engaged in prototyping and evaluating solutions to facilitate this process (e.g. latency hiding service and caches).

Collaboration with other HEP and non-HEP communities

WLCG was conceived at a time when HEP was the only scientific domain with computing and data needs large enough to require a worldwide distributed e-Infrastructure. Now, and even more so in the short-medium term, other domains are going to face similar needs and are bracing for large scale solutions. Since WLCG has demonstrated its capability to deploy and operate a large distributed system and has worldwide credibility, it is a natural partner for other sciences with large data needs. The scale of the future scientific computing infrastructures is such that it is unlikely to be affordable to have individual solutions for each of the sciences. The funding agencies favour an approach where a common set of tools and services can serve most sciences. The sciences, at the same time, need to retain the flexibility to use what is most appropriate for them and complement the ecosystem with solutions addressing their specific needs. Moving forward, collaborating with other science along these lines is one of the core aspects of the WLCG strategy. WLCG has already formalised the “partner” status in its governance, ensuring that partners are engaged in contributing to the technical evolution of services and have a voice in management level decisions in WLCG. Belle-2, DUNE, JUNO and Virgo are currently WLCG partners. WLCG also has strong links with the nuclear, astronomy and astroparticle communities through the ESCAPE Open Collaboration and a dedicated collaboration agreement with SKA. The latest discussions in the context of ECFA, NuPECC and APPEC share this vision, with the definition of common computing activities via the JENA initiative. The collaboration with these sciences enables the consolidation of efforts around a common data management ecosystem, where the vast majority of the WLCG services have been adopted by the different sciences. This process favours long term support of these components and will be a key element for software sustainability in future. Defining a governance for a global scientific computing infrastructure supporting multiple sciences remains an ambition. In the next few years the focus will be at the technical (R&D) and operational (Data Challenges) level.

WLCG has strong collaboration with other national and international initiatives developing or supporting large scale computing infrastructures, such as the Open Science Grid (OSG) in the US and the European Grid Initiative (EGI). Both infrastructures provide services in use by WLCG to federate the grid sites. At the same time, OSG has been a driver for innovation for the benefit of WLCG. Both EGI and OSG are very strong in the support of the long tail of science and WLCG intends to continue these collaborations.

Impact of WLCG on science and society

The role of WLCG in scientific computing allowed various countries to develop a research and education cyber-infrastructure for the benefit of other sciences. The clearest example is the

network infrastructure that WLCG had to develop to support increasingly challenging needs. WLCG will continue engaging in its countries to foster synergies with different national initiatives. At the same time, WLCG is planning to reach new countries, and particularly the ones in the CERN community that do not yet contribute to software and computing. The process aims to engage resource providers of any size, including new Tier-1 centers. The evolution of the WLCG middleware mentioned above in the document, is an important ingredient to favour the commitments of new smaller institutes. As part of this effort, WLCG will promote initiatives for training and education, leveraging existing platforms from the HEP Software Foundation and different labs and communities. WLCG is also engaged in supporting regional initiatives for the coordination and knowledge sharing of scientific computing. An example is the Asian Tier Center Forum, providing community building opportunities that WLCG plans to propose to other regions.

Environmental Sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a strategic area of priority for many of the WLCG federations and funding agencies. WLCG started a process to estimate the energy consumption needed by the computing equipment for the LHC experiments. A study was produced in 2023 and presented at the CHEP2023 conference. Providing information, opportunity, and incentive to help collaborators reduce the carbon footprint of computing needs should be a priority for WLCG as it is a priority of its funding agencies and a demonstration of social responsibility. WLCG plans to agree on metrics and provide a framework to collect information related to energy efficiency. WLCG also intends to facilitate the use of more energy-efficient hardware where possible, depending on the readiness of the experiment software and the common libraries. Finally, WLCG will develop and promote a sustainability plan to improve energy efficiency and reduce carbon footprint, while supporting the physics program inline with the expectations of the funding agencies. Such a plan should be covering software, computing models, facilities, and hardware technology and lifecycle.

The WLCG model for future large CERN experiments

The WLCG is operating to preserve, process and analyse the data from LHC experiments, with an expected life span from Run-1 (2009) to at least the end of LHC Operations (currently scheduled in 2041). Whatever large scale HEP experiment CERN will decide to host after LHC, it will need a similarly scaled (if not larger) computing effort. The computing model of the future experiments could in principle rely on a centralised solution, hosted at CERN, however, the distributed funding and deployment model for LHC computing has proved to be very effective in providing processing and storage services to the experiments. It has also allowed the funding agencies to invest in their national infrastructure while supporting the LHC physics program. We believe therefore that the future model will continue being distributed and funded through such in-kind contributions by the countries participating in the CERN experimental program. To support such a model, a structure such as WLCG will be needed, based on the same principles: integration of globally distributed

Exascale-level resources with services and software, within a trust framework that transcends site and national boundaries.

The history of LHC has taught us that computing needs to be designed, tested and validated alongside any other detector equipment; hence, initial thoughts and ideas for the computing of the next CERN accelerator and experiments should start in a timely manner. An extension of the current scope of WLCG to the new initiative(s) is an efficient way to benefit from the LHC experience, and to bootstrap the needed process towards the computing model of the future large CERN experiments. The WLCG mandate could be expanded accordingly, following decisions from the 2026 ESPP process.